

THE ROLE OF MODERN METHODS IN ASSESSING AND PREVENTING THE INFLUENCE OF POPULAR CULTURE ON THE MIND OF YOUTH

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INTRODUCTION

Topic relevance: It is known that popular culture affects people's alienation from their own culture, it causes young people to abandon spiritual values and ideals from the cultural heritage of past generations. This is a very dangerous situation for the future of any nation. affects the economic standard of living and the development of the state. Popular culture can become a way for young people who are prone to emotional perception to deny the moral and legal norms of society in order to achieve their goals.

The purpose of the study: Based on the relevance of the topic, the purpose of this study is to analyze the current state of popular culture among young people in our country, the negative aspects of popular culture affecting the lifestyle of young people, and to develop recommendations for the organization of a modern educational process in the fight against popular culture.

Influence of popular culture

The growing popularity of popular culture is connected with the development of the mass communication system of the society. Communication technologies enable the distribution of cultural products. Currently, the development of the mass communication system (MSC) has become very intensive, all settlements are mass communication, especially in the context of television and the Internet. At the same time, SMKLAR serves as a means of spontaneous civilization, that is, they influence the minds of unformed young people, inculcating stereotypes of mass culture in them. It should be noted that during the transitional period, the formation of the personality of young people in a virtual lifestyle leads to their becoming victims of mass culture.

The negative consequences of the influence of popular culture on young people are as follows: promotion of material values, popularization of consumer culture, increase of demands and expectations of society, direction to recreation and entertainment sphere. This, in turn, leads to a decrease in the role of spiritual values and an increase in deviations.

Mass culture among young people has become a transitional stage in the life of young people. With the end of the process of socialization and entering adulthood, young people become consumers of mass culture or prefer high culture, in one way or another they remain loyal to some elements of youth culture. The most dangerous part is that this cultural attack is absorbed into the

life style of young people throughout their lives. is destined to lead to a revolution.

Our research

Based on the above, in order to assess the current state of popular culture among youth in our country, the negative impact of popular culture on the quality of life of young people was analyzed:

In the questionnaire, the following aspects of the negative influence of popular culture on young people were identified

- Decreasing the general level of the spiritual culture of society,
- Bringing the youth to standardize and unify the way of life, but also the way of thinking of millions of people;
- Artificial needs; Using modern media, it replaces real life for many people, imposes certain ideas and preferences
- Influence of speech culture on language standards
- Influence on national values, dress, culture

The result

According to the results of the questionnaires conducted among the students of the National University of Uzbekistan in the above directions, according to the opinion of the participants, one of the most negative effects of mass culture in the life of today's youth was assessed as moral corruption and the appearance of passive culture.

Recommendations

Modern means of education and training in preventing the popularization of popular culture among young people

1. First of all, parents should set an example for their children regarding cultural views
2. Formation of children's culture of correct use of social media materials
3. Promotion of a healthy lifestyle
4. Organization of an educational process that helps to deeply understand the importance of national values, religious and worldly sciences
5. Increasing the value of young people in the family and society
6. To support the opinions of young people
7. Increasing social media materials promoting our national values
8. Starting the educational process based on our oriental culture from the kindergarten age

Conclusion

According to the results of the research, one of the most negative effects of mass culture in the life of today's youth was assessed as moral corruption and the appearance of passive culture. Based on this situation, it can be said that not only young people, but also adults should arm themselves with creative ideas against destructive ideas, and it should be beneficial for everyone.

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